

COVID^X

Get to know more about INNO4COV-19, our project partner for the final event!

In September **COVID-X and INNO4COV-19** will highlight innovation developed by European companies and will provide opportunities for projects to showcase their results. There will be time and room for exhibition, networking and round tables.

Stay tuned for upcoming details about the event!

[Read more about INNO4COV-19](#)

Join us on the 23rd of June for this clinical event!

COVID Management and lessons learned in medicine, Challenges in Healthcare systems or AI tools and how to improve healthcare services will be some of the topics to be addressed!

Meet the Game Changer working with SERMAS!

Get to know more about **SEGTRAN** within the #COVIDXSuccessStories! A Scientific Solution that Bridges Nations at COVID-19 War Time: The Aim is a Global Defence Against Any Virus.

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Our collaborations:

We work with a range of parallel projects in common areas of research to maximise our impact and network reach.

Have a look!

COVID-X

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